

EFFECTIVENESS OF PART-TIME INSTRUCTORS IN THE PHILIPPINE HIGHER EDUCATION CONTEXT

Eden Grace V. Tabanao, Holly Marie Grace D. Isaran, Macbeth Jew II L. Icalina,
Ace G. Rebusquillo, Kent Niño E. Villagonzalo

*Social Science Department, Negros Oriental State University – Guihulngan Campus,
Guihulngan City, Negros Oriental, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the instructional effectiveness of part-time instructors in higher education by examining their demographic profiles, self-reported teaching contributions, and student evaluation ratings using the quality assurance system. Specifically, it aimed to determine whether factors such as age, gender, educational attainment, workload, and training background influenced their performance and student feedback. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were collected through surveys and evaluation forms. Findings revealed that most part-time instructors were aged 26–30, had master's units, handled heavy teaching loads, and had limited international training, yet received excellent ratings in instructional effectiveness (4.63), student engagement (4.56), and professional expertise (4.30). No significant correlations were found between demographic variables and contribution ratings, nor between contributions and student evaluation scores. The study concludes that teaching effectiveness is not determined by demographic characteristics but may depend on institutional support. It recommends policy enhancements to ensure equitable access to training and development opportunities for part-time faculty.

Keywords: *Effectiveness, higher educational institution, part-time instructors, student evaluation, teaching effectiveness.*

INTRODUCTION

Persistent problems such as lack of student retention and poor academic success rates are commonly experienced in higher education institutions, often linked to the growing reliance on part-time faculty. Colleges and universities have increasingly shifted their recruitment strategies toward employing temporary or part-time educators, a trend that has significant implications for educational quality, teacher welfare, and institutional policy development. This shift raises widespread concern regarding job security, working conditions, and the overall professional future of contingent faculty most particularly part-time instructors, and how these factors ultimately affect student learning outcomes (Hurlburt & McGarrah, 2016).

The hiring of part-time faculty members often stems from financial constraints and the need for flexible workforce management (Rice & Curt ,2018). Alsunaydi (2020) found that this growing dependence on temporary instructors influences institutional governance, academic autonomy, and the pursuit of regional missions. Although regional universities typically provide a more personal learning environment through smaller class sizes and community-oriented settings, the increase in part-time faculty employment brings both opportunities and challenges (Rice & Curt ,2018). While this practice allows for flexibility and cost efficiency, it may also result in the marginalization of part-time instructors, who often experience limited institutional engagement and job satisfaction.

According to Anthony et al. (2020), part-time instructors constitute an essential component of higher education, particularly in two- and four-year institutions, yet their contributions remain underexamined. Despite their potential to enrich classroom instruction with diverse professional experiences, many part-time instructors remain disconnected from the institutional culture and unaware of university policies or available support systems due to inadequate onboarding. Henkel and Haley (2020) emphasized that these instructors face numerous challenges, including limited job security, insufficient compensation, and restricted access to professional development opportunities. Moreover, Baker and DiPiro (2019) highlighted the scarcity of research focusing on the onboarding and integration of new part-time faculty members.

The Community College Research Center (CCRC, 2018) defines part-time faculty as instructors employed in higher education without full-time status. This arrangement allows institutions to offer a wider range of courses and respond to the changing demands of the labor market. However, as Bickerstaff and Chavarín (2018) observed, the increasing reliance on part-time instructors makes them instrumental to institutional success particularly in community colleges, yet they often remain excluded from key developmental and governance processes. Green and Morales (2021) further reported that most professional development programs disproportionately serve full-time faculty, leaving part-time instructors with minimal opportunities for career growth and instructional improvement.

Recognizing these disparities aligns with Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), which advocates for inclusive and equitable quality education and the promotion of

lifelong learning opportunities for all. Ensuring that both full-time and part-time educators are adequately supported, trained, and valued is essential to achieving this global goal. The researchers of this study contend that neglecting the professional needs and contributions of part-time faculty may undermine institutional effectiveness and educational equity.

Therefore, this study, conducted at Negros Oriental State University – Guihulngan Campus, seeks to examine whether the demographic characteristics of part-time instructors, such as age, gender, educational attainment, workload, and teaching experience, affect their contributions across five key areas: instructional effectiveness, student support engagement, professional experience, teaching capacity enhancement, and course scheduling flexibility. Furthermore, the study analyzes student rating scores using the QUAMC system, focusing on indicators such as commitment, knowledge, encouragement of independent learning, and classroom organization.

By investigating these relationships, the researchers of this study aim to determine whether demographic characteristics correlate with performance and student evaluations. The results are expected to fill a research gap in understanding part-time faculty dynamics within higher education, provide empirical evidence for policy formulation, and support institutional strategies toward achieving SDG 4 – Quality Education by fostering equitable and effective teaching practices for all educators.

Research Questions

This study aimed to unveil the contributions of part-time instructors in higher educational institutions. Specifically, the study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is their demographic and job profile in terms of the following areas:
 - 1.1. Age
 - 1.2. Sex
 - 1.3. Highest educational attainment
 - 1.4. Number of hours per week
 - 1.5. Number of years in teaching
 - 1.6. Seminars and training attended
 - 1.7. College affiliation
2. What is the level of contribution of the Part-time instructors in NORSU-Guihulngan terms of:
 - 2.1. Instructional Effectiveness
 - 2.2. Student Support Engagement
 - 2.3. Professional Expertise
 - 2.4. Teaching Capacity Enhancement
 - 2.5. Flexibility in Course Scheduling
3. What is the student evaluation ratings of part-time instructors during QUAMC evaluation in terms of:
 - 3.1. Commitment
 - 3.2. Knowledge

3.3. Teaching for independent learning

3.4. Management of Learning

4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondent's demographic profile and the level of part-time instructors' contributions?

5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of contributions and the students' evaluation ratings of part-time instructors during QUAMC evaluation?

METHODOLOGY

This study involved 43 part-time instructors from a state university in Negros Oriental, Philippines. The participants represented various colleges, disciplines, and academic backgrounds within the institution. Their inclusion was based on availability, willingness to participate, and capacity to provide informed perspectives grounded in their teaching experiences. To ensure equitable representation across departments, the researchers employed a stratified random sampling technique. The total population of part-time instructors was first identified through coordination with the human resource office, which provided the necessary demographic information. The sample was then stratified according to key variables such as age, sex, educational attainment, years of experience, workload, seminars and training attended, and college affiliation. From each stratum, participants were randomly selected to minimize bias and enhance representativeness.

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the relationship between the demographic profiles of part-time instructors and their instructional contributions. It specifically examined how variables such as age, educational background, years of teaching experience, and seminar attendance relate to instructional effectiveness, student engagement, and professional performance as evaluated through the university's Quality Assurance Monitoring and Control (QUAMC) system. Data were collected using a researcher-made questionnaire composed of three sections: demographic profile, contributions of part-time instructors, and student evaluation results from QUAMC. The instrument underwent expert validation by three Ph.D. holders, receiving a mean validity rating of 4.3, which indicates high validity. To test reliability, a pilot study involving 30 respondents was conducted, yielding a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.86, signifying good internal consistency. The questionnaire utilized a Likert scale and was carefully aligned with the study's constructs and objectives.

Before data collection, formal letters were submitted to the campus director and college deans to secure permission to conduct the study. Upon approval, questionnaires were distributed to the sampled participants, who were provided with clear instructions and informed consent forms. Completed questionnaires were retrieved, checked for completeness, and encoded for analysis, while student evaluation data were obtained from QUAMC to supplement the correlational analysis. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used to summarize the demographic profiles, while weighted means were computed to assess the perceived level of instructional contribution and corresponding student evaluations. The weighted ratings were interpreted using the following scale: 4.21–5.00 (Excellent), 3.41–4.20 (Very Good), 2.61–3.40 (Good), 1.81–

2.60 (Fair), and 1.00–1.80 (Poor). To determine the relationships between variables, the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was applied to analyze the associations between instructor profiles, instructional contributions, and student evaluation results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
20-25 years old	16	37
26-30 years old	9	21
31-35 years old	1	2
36-40 years old	3	7
41 and above	14	33
Sex	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	20	47
Female	10	23
Prefer not to say	13	30
Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Bachelor's Degree	6	14
With Masters Units	35	81
With Master's Degree	2	5
With Doctorate Units	0	0
With Doctorate Degree	0	0
Number of Hours per Week	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Minimal Load (9-15 hours)	0	0
Moderate Load (18-21 hours)	2	5
Substantial Load (24-29 hours)	5	12
Heavy Load (30-36 hours)	36	84
Number of Years in Teaching	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
0-2 years	30	70
3-5 years	8	19
6-10 years	4	9
11-15 years	0	0
16-above	1	2
Seminars and Training Attended	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Regional or Local	26	60
National	15	35
International	2	5
College Affiliation	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
College of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	2	5
College of Arts and Sciences	20	47
College of Business Administration	7	16

College of Criminal Justice Education	3	7
College of Industrial Technology	8	19
College of Teacher Education	3	7

The Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of hours per week, number of years in teaching, seminars and training attended, and college affiliation. The highest age group is 26-30 years old (37%), which drastically drops to 2 percent in the 36-40 age group, indicating a young workforce (Gacusan and Calangi, 2022). Regarding sex, the largest percentage is male (47%), followed by females (23%), and a substantial number of individuals (30%) prefer to not specify their gender, although this hinders a clear analysis based on the gender ratio. This substantial number of non-disclosed responses may reflect sensitivities surrounding gender identity or a desire for privacy. Creating an inclusive institutional environment where individuals feel safe and respected in expressing their identities is critical. Hayes (2024), emphasizes the importance of leveraging demographic data to develop identity-specific support systems. Furthermore, an overwhelming 81% possess "Master's Units," highlighting a strong pursuit of advanced education, though no respondents reported doctoral qualifications, which aligns with research on part-time instructors' professional development. Cabello et al. (2022) and Eney and Davidson (2014) support the view that advanced academic qualifications are correlated with increased professional development and improved teaching quality.

The statistics also indicate very challenging working environment and a predominantly early-career teaching staff. 84% of the people interviewed carry a "Heavy Load (30-36 hours)" weekly, which suggests a high level of professional intensity and possible lack of work-life balance. An increased load means increased paycheck to many part-time instructors and this may be a motivating force, given that many part-time instructors do not get full time benefits. Such duality implies that workload cannot be considered only as burden but as potential source of financial stability. At the same time, the majority of respondents (70%) have 0-2 years of teaching experience which indicates the significant input of new teachers. This is contrary to low representation in the 11-15 years' experience bracket. Finally, professional development activities are largely concentrated at the "Regional or Local" level (60%), with minimal international participation (5%). This implies that either local training opportunities are preferred or accessible. The college of Arts and Science (CAS) has the highest affiliation of 47% whereas the College of Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries (CAFF) has the lowest of 5%. This disproportionate representation means that certain colleges depend more on part-time faculty especially in general education and large enrollments sections. Kezar (2022) found that the college setting, and access to resources, have a profound impact on the teaching performance of instructors. This relationship has its challenge and opportunities and although part-time faculty members may not receive the same support across the board, depending on the department, they are individuals with variety of experiences that can enhance the academic life. Institutions must acknowledge these variations and offer departmentalized orientations, support systems and professional growth experiences.

Table 2. Level of contributions of the Part-time Instructors

Variable	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Instructional Effectiveness	4.32	Excellent
Student Support Engagement	4.56	Excellent
Professional Expertise	4.27	Excellent
Teaching Capacity Enhancement	4.14	Very Good
Flexibility in Course Scheduling	4.02	Very Good
Overall Mean	4.26	Excellent

The Statistics in Table 2 reveal the highest mean score of 4.63, interpreted as “Excellent,” under the aspect of Student Support Engagement. This could imply that part-time instructors are so much engaged in student-centered teaching by making themselves approachable, responsive, and support to the students within and outside classroom. This observation concurs with the observation of a study conducted by Paterson (2017), which highlighted that part-time instructors tend to develop healthy interpersonal relations with students, resulting in better academic guidance and mentorship. Though institutional integration is minimal, part-time instructors are still committed to student success, delivering academic guidance regularly and showing consideration to individual student issues (Ran and Sanders, 2020).

On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.49, interpreted as “Very Good,” was observed in the aspect of Flexibility in Course Scheduling. This could imply that although part-time instructors are willing to be flexible with their schedule, some of them might have difficulties in providing evening classes because of personal time limitation, teaching load in various institutions, or even absence of support in flexible scheduling systems. According to the study conducted by Rossol-Allison & Beyers (2011), illuminates the value of flexibility in the classes that may meet various needs of different students and result in inclusive learning. Nevertheless, part-time instructors may not be able to exercise complete flexibility in this aspect due to logistical constraints (i.e. lack of classrooms, scheduling conflicts, institutional restrictions, etc.). The total mean score of 4.26 that can be translated as Excellent may indicate that students significantly appreciate the work of part-time instructors and in particular, their teaching effectiveness, support engagement, and professional knowledge. It indicates that despite limited opportunities in institutional resources and professional growth, part-time faculty members continue to play an active role in providing quality higher education by offering additional support and academic advising to students (Durso, 2011). The continuing problem of part-time instructors is the issue of inclusion and access to institutional resources, yet their proven excellence, especially in the area of engagement with students, cannot be ignored in the effectiveness of higher education. Institutions that prioritize their development and integration will not only improve instructional quality but also better meet the evolving needs of students.

Table 3. Students' Evaluation Ratings of Part-time Instructors During Quality Assurance Management Center (QUAMC) evaluation.

Variable	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Commitment	4.37	Excellent
Knowledge	4.39	Excellent
Teaching for independent learning	4.41	Excellent
Management of Learning	4.39	Excellent
Overall Mean	4.39	Excellent

The statistics in Table 3 presents students' evaluation ratings of part-time instructors during the QUAMC evaluation, showing consistently high performance across all indicators. The highest mean score of 4.41 was recorded in Teaching for Independent Learning, interpreted as “Excellent”. This indicates that the part-time instructors are indeed preparing the skills in the students towards self-directed learning, critical thinking, and academic independence. Instructors who can be seen as promoting independent learning can be evaluated more positively by the students, as they can make learners be in charge of their educational advancement (Snow et al., 2022). Conversely, the lowest mean score of 4.37 was depicted in the domain of Commitment. This observation aligns with Benton and Cashin (2018), who had stated that part-time faculty tend to shine despite having little training and resource accessibility. The identical mean ratings of 4.39 in Knowledge and in Management of Learning indicate the stability of excellence in mastering subjects and in organizing the classroom. Part-time instructors seem to score highly in Knowledge as they are perceived to be experts, able to simplify complicated concepts, and able to incorporate real-world industry experience into the classroom. The benefit of including experienced teachers in curriculum development processes, as it makes them remain relevant and significant to learners (Carl, 2009). These findings demonstrate that effective instruction depends on lesson planning, maintaining a well-organized classroom and providing timely feedback.

The overall mean score of 4.39, interpreted as “Excellent”, reflects a consistently high level of student satisfaction across all evaluated areas of instruction. Nevertheless, the steadily high ratings also make it clear that institutions should allocate more resources to the development of part-time faculty to maintain and continue to improve the quality of instruction. These general performances suggest that part-time instructors have contributed highly on the academic quality and student performance outcomes in the QUAMC assessment period. Universities ought to react to this by giving equal opportunities to faculty development resources and by integrating part-time faculty into the departmental planning and academic decision-making procedure.

Table 4. The Significant Relationship between the Demographic Profile and the Level of Contributions

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	P-value	Decision for Ho	Remark
Age	-0.04	0.40	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Gender	-0.04	0.53	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Highest Education	-0.14	0.27	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Number of Hours per Week	0.05	0.63	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Number of Hours in Teaching	0.01	0.83	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Seminars and Training Attended	-0.06	0.53	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
College Affiliation	-0.07	0.06	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Overall Rating	-0.04	0.46	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant

**Highly Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.0*

**Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05*

**Not Significant is greater than 0.05*

The data in Table 4 presents the test of the significant relationship between part-time instructors' demographic profile and their level of contributions. This result shows that there is no significant relationship between part-time instructors' demographic profiles—such as age (0.40), gender (0.53), highest educational attainment (0.27), number of hours per week (0.63), number of hours in teaching (0.83), seminars and training attended (0.53), college affiliation (0.06), and overall rating (0.46)—and their level of contributions. This suggests that the background characteristics of part-time instructors do not directly affect their teaching contributions or overall instructional performance.

The result above was in contrast with the result of the study conducted by Hanson et al. (2018), concluded that part-time instructors holding professional degrees in teaching felt more confident and believed they were better positioned to offer effective instruction. However, the current data imply that regardless of educational attainment or teaching load, all part-time instructors can contribute effectively when given equal opportunity. Conversely, the finding correlates with Hanson et al. (2018), which proposed that despite minimal training or unreliable work circumstances, part time instructors are still competent teachers. Part-time instructors, although having disparate preparation experiences, demonstrate the same possibility to succeed when provided with fair institutional resources and support (Kezar, 2020). Hence, addressing the aspect of environmental and structural support can be more fruitful than concentrating on demographic predictors in case of expecting to improve teaching performance among part-time educators. These results suggest the significance of support structures within institutions and fair access to professional development as opposed to concentrating on demographic features alone in the quest to enhance teaching performance.

Table 5. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Contributions and the Students' Evaluation Ratings of Part-time Instructors during QUAMC Evaluation.

Variables	Correlation Coefficient	P-value	Decision for Ho	Remark
Instructional Effectiveness	0.02	0.61	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Student Support Engagement	-0.02	0.62	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Professional Experience	0.03	0.34	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Teaching Capacity Enhancement	-0.01	0.63	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Flexibility in Course Scheduling	-0.01	0.76	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant
Overall Rating	0.002	0.59	Do not Reject Ho	Not Significant

**Highly Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.0*

**Significant if p-value is lesser than 0.05*

**Not Significant is greater than 0.05*

The data in Table 5 presents all P-values are greater than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is not rejected. This means there is no significant relationship between the level of contributions of part-time instructors across the areas of instructional effectiveness (0.61), student support engagement (0.62), professional experience (0.34), teaching capacity enhancement (0.63), and flexibility in course scheduling (0.76)—and the students' evaluation ratings during the QUAMC evaluation. Even the overall rating, with a P-value of 0.59, was found to be not significant. This finding indicates that the ratings of part-time instructors by students do not necessarily mirror the quantity or the extent of the contributions of these instructors to the teaching and to the institutional objectives. Students tend to rate instructors according to teaching quality perception, professional knowledge, and classroom dynamics (Hanson et al., 2018). The negligence of correlation in this research might reflect that the student rating is being affected by other variables in the place of the overall institutional contributions of instructors like personality, communication style, or grading leniency. According to Kamps and Engelhard (2011), part-time instructors who employ real-world experience, promote student autonomy, and exhibit passion in their teaching are likely to be highly rated. These findings indicate that even though part-time instructors might bring rich input in terms of instruction quality, student engagement, and professional knowledge, it does not directly convey into student evaluation ratings. This underscores the importance of institutions to adopt a more comprehensive assessment method that encompasses peer-review, administrative-assessment and self-assessment with student feedback as a more valid gauge of teaching contributions.

Conclusions

The study revealed that part-time instructors within the university context are predominantly early-career professionals with limited teaching experience, with 70% having only 0–2 years in the profession. Most of them handle heavy teaching loads (84%) and do so without the benefits accorded to full-time employment. Despite these constraints, a majority possess or are pursuing postgraduate qualifications, with 81% currently enrolled in master's degree programs—reflecting a strong commitment to academic and professional growth. While much of their professional development is obtained from local and regional training opportunities, their instructional contributions were consistently rated as excellent, particularly in the areas of student support engagement, instructional effectiveness, and professional expertise, as indicated by a high overall mean rating of 4.26.

Student evaluations from the QUAMC system reinforced these findings, revealing excellent ratings across all domains, especially in promoting independent learning, which achieved a mean score of 4.41. Nonetheless, course scheduling flexibility received slightly lower ratings, possibly due to limited time availability and institutional scheduling constraints. The results also indicated no significant correlation between the instructors' demographic characteristics and their instructional contributions, nor between their contributions and student evaluation scores. This suggests that teaching excellence among part-time faculty is not primarily determined by demographic or experiential factors but may instead be influenced by intrinsic motivation, institutional support, and a conducive teaching environment.

These findings underscore the vital role that part-time instructors play in ensuring instructional quality and fostering student engagement in higher education. However, the absence of significant correlations between contributions and student evaluations implies the need for a more comprehensive and multidimensional evaluation framework that integrates peer assessments, administrative reviews, and self-evaluations alongside student feedback. The researchers recommend that institutions strengthen the integration, orientation, and continuous professional development of part-time faculty while providing equitable access to institutional resources.

Moreover, this study contributes to the advancement of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) by emphasizing the importance of inclusive, equitable, and quality teaching practices. By recognizing and empowering part-time instructors as integral partners in delivering quality education, higher education institutions can enhance instructional outcomes, support lifelong learning opportunities, and promote an environment where both educators and learners can thrive. This alignment with SDG 4 highlights the essential role of institutional policies and support systems in achieving educational equity and excellence at all levels.

Recommendations

In light of the findings, the researchers recommend that higher education institutions strengthen the support systems, professional development programs, and institutional integration of part-time instructors. Given that many of these instructors are early in their teaching careers and handle heavy workloads without full-time benefits, the university should develop structured onboarding programs, mentorship initiatives, and flexible scheduling systems to improve their work-life balance and instructional performance. These initiatives would not only enhance teaching effectiveness but also contribute to the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (Quality Education) by ensuring equitable access to professional growth opportunities for all educators.

Institutions are further encouraged to design inclusive policies that provide part-time faculty with access to the same academic resources, seminars, and research opportunities available to full-time staff. Strengthening collaboration between part-time and full-time instructors through joint workshops and peer mentoring can promote a more cohesive academic environment and foster shared pedagogical innovation. Additionally, revising faculty evaluation systems to include multiple dimensions—such as peer evaluation, administrative assessment, and self-reflection—alongside student feedback may provide a more holistic understanding of instructional performance.

Future research is recommended to validate the findings of this study across larger populations and multiple campuses, as well as to include qualitative approaches such as interviews or focus group discussions to explore deeper insights into the lived experiences of part-time instructors. Studies comparing public and private higher education institutions, or full-time versus part-time teaching dynamics, may also reveal additional factors influencing teaching effectiveness and satisfaction. Furthermore, longitudinal research examining the long-term impacts of institutional support and professional development on part-time instructors' performance would provide valuable evidence for policy formulation.

By implementing these recommendations, universities can not only improve instructional quality and faculty satisfaction but also advance the global pursuit of inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education, as envisioned in SDG 4.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research strictly adhered to ethical guidelines to protect the rights and welfare of all participants. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents, detailing the study's purpose, their rights, and their freedom to withdraw at any time. Participant anonymity and confidentiality were ensured by aggregating data and storing it securely. The collected data were used exclusively for this study and handled with the utmost respect. The study also received institutional approval before any data collection commenced. Researchers maintained objectivity and transparency in reporting results and acknowledged the study's limitations. These ethical practices were implemented to foster

trust, validity, and the responsible use of research findings for policy and academic development.

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